

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TEACHING PROFESSIONALLY-ORIENTED ENGLISH IN A BUSINESS SCHOOL (DIFFERENT APPROACH)

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Abstract

In the article, the author tried to show how teaching of this discipline differs from the teaching of other language disciplines, as well as the reasons and necessity of the described approach to teaching Professionally-oriented English language from their point of view.

Keywords: Professional language, management, business, difference, writing, speaking.

Professionally-oriented foreign language is a discipline taught in Almaty Management University (AlmaU) in the 3rd year of academic studies. Students come to this course with a solid background in the English language, acquired in their first and second years, having studied a course in General English and the basics of Academic writing.

Before starting the Professional course, students are supposed to take the ELPT (English Language Proficiency Test) exam, and after successful completion of it, they are allowed to enter the course. The test was designed by the group of experienced teachers on the basis of the Ielts and First Certificate international exams. High-level students (Upper-Intermediate and High Intermediate) are allowed to take the Professionally-oriented Foreign language course.

First-year students enter the AlmaU having different levels of the English language awareness, from Elementary to Upper-Intermediate; thus, not all students are ready to go through the Professional English course at the beginning of their 3rd year as they do not meet the requirements of the course. The course duration is one semester, consequently, some students are able to join the course in the second half of their 3rd academic year after they have improved their English language proficiency level. Actually, students themselves are responsible for achieving the level of a foreign language necessary for studying in the third year of their bachelor academic studies.

As a matter of fact, the overwhelming majority of 3rd-year students have equally good level of the English language, so there is no division of people into groups by a language awareness level.

Professionally-oriented Foreign Language course is designed to develop key skills in Professional English of Management and Business related major disciplines forming communicative competences of students in some spheres of business environment (Work and motivation; Marketing; People management; Customer service; IT; Cybersecurity, and some others); and creating independent learners who take responsibility for their learning situation. This can be reached due to the interesting and well-organized content according to the students' needs and interests, and in accordance with the course requirements. The continuous assessment on the part of the teachers will encourage students to be responsible for fulfilling the tasks regularly and meeting the deadlines. A student-centered approach

used in teaching focuses on obtaining problem-solving and thinking skills. The emphasis should be made on creative learning process and learning environment that will facilitate it for students to analyze and reflect upon the process of learning and realizing the results they have achieved.

The course is based on *Business result* UI course-book by Oxford University Press and another educational source *Career paths* by Express publishing. The focus of the course is on the formation of writing and speaking skills, and the use of language in a meaningful and authentic context. The approach to working on linguistic material is communicative. The course incorporates career-specific vocabulary and contexts that immerse students in the four key language components: reading, listening, speaking and writing.

Among the learning outcomes of the course can be mentioned the following:

- Gaining knowledge of special terminology in different spheres of business activity, such as economics, finance, management and marketing;
- Deepening the understanding of global business processes;
- Learning main concepts of doing business in English through developing certain abilities to act in typical business situations;
- Mastering communication skills for meetings, presentations, business communication and phone calls;
- Application of various strategies and strategic recommendations to solve the company's business issues;
- Ability to write official documents (CV, Cover letter, Reports, etc.), and some others.

What are the features that make the Professional course different from those we are used to teaching?

1. Due to the fact that we have students of different specialties in academic groups (management and marketing, accounting and audit, social sciences, hotel management and catering business, IT and technical support, and others), the professionally-oriented English course is subdivided into three main courses – Management and Business, Social Sciences, Hotel and Catering management, and Tourism.

2. The above-mentioned courses provide general information and business terminology of business envi-

ronment, and business skills to meet the needs of students of all specialties in Professionally-oriented English language groups. For example, the course contains not only general principles and basics of management but also related to it topics, like creating a company website taking into account the peculiarities of the Kazakhstani context that is interesting and beneficial for both marketeers and IT specialists.

3. As it was said before, the educational focus in the 3rd-year program is on teaching and practicing productive business skills, i.e. writing and speaking.

The course gives practice and consolidation of the following business skills in writing and business communication:

Writing

Students are able to:

- Describe a management style used in a company; express their satisfaction/ dissatisfaction with working conditions and suggest the ways to improve them talking about openness of the management, decision-making process, authority and responsibility delegation, control and assessment, etc.)

- Write an informational letter about the company to send to prospective customers describing company's products, achievements and recent developments.

- Write impressive CV and Cover letter including personal information, working experience/ responsibilities, skills, recent accomplishments, etc.

- Write about how information technologies change their company's business; compare their business without using IT and with.

- Write a letter to their partner to make a proposal/counter proposal discussing the payment terms and/or asking for a discount.

- Write a message to a shipping company applying for information and rate quotation

- Make up SWOT/PEST analyses for a company

Speaking

SS are able to:

- Run a meeting as a chairperson, introduce the topic and the agenda of the meeting; ask for the opinion of the participants giving them the floor; summarize the results and agreements achieved at the meeting

- Discuss the candidates for a position in a company focusing on their strengths and weaknesses, as well as their personalities to make the right choice as Head of the department

- Make a well-structured Power Point presentation about the company/start up using the tools for linking ideas and the techniques for attracting the attention of the audience

- Negotiate a deal with a partner company on the phone discussing the price, quantity and payment terms

- Conducting/participating in a job interview answering different questions related to their area of business and working experience

- Speak about risks the company may face dividing them into 4 categories: political, economic, social and cultural, technological (PEST analysis).

4. The system of assessment is also different from a traditional one used at the University while teaching General English, for example. The Professionally-oriented English language intermediate (Midterm) test score is the average score of 3-4 units' assignments covered during the period of academic studies, that is 7-8 weeks.

In turn, tasks for individual units contain one written and one oral task on the topic being covered. For example,

We eks	Topic/Module	Format of the class	Assignments (SROP/SRO)
1-2	Introduction to the course Unit 1. First impression	Discussion/ giving presentations	Mini presentation (Ex. 6, p.10)
3-4	Unit 2. Work & Motivation	Discussion /interviews	Writing a CV/Cover letter. Speaking- a job interview

Picture 1 (an excerpt from the author's syllabus)

The scores for these tasks are added up and divided by the number of tasks, which is the final Midterm score.

The advantage of this approach to assessing students' performance is, in our opinion, that a certain skill is tested immediately after passing and practicing this skill. The very fact that this grade is officially part of the Midterm final score makes students take it more seriously. In this way, it is possible to avoid ignoring

some of the skills and business terminology for individual units when using a common test at the end of the training period.

5. One of the main requirements for students' course works is the use of the Kazakhstani context, i.e. it should be, for example, an information letter advertising a real Kazakh company achievements and recent innovations, or a SWOT analysis of a business idea that they propose to develop a real startup in the republic, etc.

6. Final projects after the completion of the course should be again based on the local context and include some of the following topics relating to different areas of students' specialization:

- Human resources management
- Production and Operations management
- People management (management styles)
- Business expansion/Mergers and acquisitions
- International marketing/Selling online/Brands
- Neuromarketing
- Logistics
- Cybersecurity
- IT and Technical support
- Raising capital and start-ups
- Business communication and negotiations.

Cross-cultural communication. (Doing business in Kazakhstan), and others by students' choice

References

1. Business Partner, A2+. Coursebook by M. O'Keeffe, et al., Pearson, 2018
2. Business Partner, B2. Coursebook by Iwonna Dubicka, et al., Pearson, 2018
3. Business Result, Advanced. Student's Book by Kate Baad, et al., Oxford University Press, 2013
4. Business Result, Intermediate, Second edition. Student's Book by John Hughes & Jon Nauton, Oxford University Press, 2017
5. Business Result, Upper-Intermediate. Student's Book by Michael Duckworth & Rebecca Turner, Oxford University Press, 2012
6. Career Paths, Management I, II, V. Evans, J. Dooley, Express Publishing
7. Skills for Business Studies, Upper-Intermediate, by Louis Rogers, Oxford, 2012

ОСНОВНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РЕФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ВСТУПИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЭКЗАМЕНОВ В ВУЗЫ КНР

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THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF REFORMING THE SYSTEM OF ENTRANCE EXAMINATIONS TO UNIVERSITIES OF THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA

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Аннотация

В статье анализируются особенности системы вступительных экзаменов в высшие учебные заведения КНР, рассмотрены преимущества и недостатки «гаокао» с точки зрения равного справедливого доступа к образованию, выявлены основные направления реформирования системы вступительных экзаменов в КНР и связанные с ними изменения в содержании школьного образования.

Abstract

This article investigates a series of characteristics of China's National College Entrance Examination (NCEE), commonly known as the Gaokao, involving the fairness of the Gaokao, the advantages, and disadvantages of the Gaokao exam system. Besides, this research puts forward the reform orientation of the Gaokao and based on this, makes recommendations for the development of China's middle school education.

Ключевые слова: вступительные экзамены, система «гаокао», реформирование системы образования, средняя школа высшей ступени, справедливый доступ к образованию.

Keywords: China's National College Entrance Examination (NCEE), the Gaokao exam system, reform of education system, higher secondary school, fairness of the Gaokao.

Введение. За последние четыре десятилетия Китай прошёл сложный путь от ликвидации неграмотности значительной части населения к созданию одной из наиболее эффективных систем образования в мире. Об этом свидетельствуют высокие места китайских университетов в мировых рейтингах, различные международные исследования. Так, в 2009 году школьники Шанхая впервые приняли участие в исследовании качества образования на основе теста PISA и показали наивысшие результаты по математической грамотности со средним баллом 600 (средний балл по странам ОЭСР — 496) и сред-

ним баллом 575 по естественнонаучной грамотности (в странах ОЭСР — 501). В 2012, 2015 и 2018 годах КНР (город Шанхай и три провинции) занял места в первой десятке с незначительным отрывом от лидеров [1].

Результаты PISA наглядно демонстрируют, что Китай в начале нового тысячелетия превратился в страну, успешно модернизирующую систему образования, страну, которой удалось увязать глобальные вызовы и национальные особенности в проектировании и реализации образовательных реформ. Однако, являясь одной из самых конкурентных в